

On Hull-Propeller-Rudder Interaction and Propeller Design for a Ship with Wind-Assisted Propulsion

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Abstract. A hull and propeller optimization study of a bulk carrier fitted with rotor sails was performed within the EU-project OPTIWISE. Due to the wind propulsion by the rotor sails, the ship will sail at a certain drift angle requiring a rudder angle to keep a straight course. The hull-propeller-rudder interaction is studied for these conditions. Also, a propeller optimization study was performed for maximum efficiency and acceptable propeller-induced hull forces whilst meeting cavitation erosion constraints. The interaction between the hull, propeller and rudder was investigated by performing RANS-BEM calculations for self-propulsion conditions at relevant loading conditions and the most prevalent wind conditions following from routing simulations. When the wind forces were large, the low propeller loading with a low thrust deduction resulted in a net lower hydrodynamic force on the hull than for the case without any wind propulsion (at the same speed) with a lower engine power consumption. However, for the ballast condition several propulsive wind conditions lead to larger drift and rudder angles with a net increase in engine power. Therefore, in some conditions it appeared unfavourable to use wind-assisted propulsion. The study also shows that the rudder generates a positive thrust in certain loading and wind conditions. At very low propeller loading conditions the rudder at high angles was found to be very close to stalling. For the presented bulk carrier with retrofitted rotor sails, it was concluded that the additional operational conditions when operating the rotor sails had no effect on the propeller design and performance.

Keywords: *wind-assisted propulsion, bulk carrier, RANS-BEM, propeller optimization*

1. Introduction

In 2018 the shipping industry was responsible for around 2.9% of the global emissions of GHG caused by human activities [1]. Prognoses show that the emissions from 2008 could increase with 130% by the year 2050 [2]. If these prognoses are true, the Paris Agreement will not be adhered. In order to oppose the prognoses, the shipping industry should reduce the amount of fuel used, search for cleaner fuels, or even alternative ways of propulsion. One alternative way of propulsion is wind propulsion. Wind is a free source of energy without emissions. Wind propulsion is used since the beginning of the shipping but largely disappeared from the scene for the commercial shipping when in the end of the 1800s with the merchant fleet transitioning from wood to iron and steel construction allowing for larger ships to be built and the compound steam engine offering a more practical and economical method to propel the ship [3]. Nowadays, wind-assisted propulsion is making a comeback for the commercial shipping to reduce the GHG emissions and save fuel costs. Wind propulsion technologies could reduce the engine power demands by 5 to 15% without changing its operation or ship design [4]. When changing the design and operations more savings could be achieved. Many studies on wind-assist focus on retrofits and to find the optimal type of device and arrangement [5][6][7]. Other studies are performed on route optimization and on the optimal hull design [8][9][10]. A less researched area is however the design and optimization of a propeller for a wind-assisted ship. The propulsion by wind is in most cases not enough yet and therefore the ship is still dependent on propeller thrust.

Molland and Hawksley [11], performed a study on the matching of the engine with the propeller of two wind-assisted ships, a coaster and a cargo ship and concluded the ships may not hold a constant speed for adverse winds.

Next to that, an engine with small power margins can result in problems with the revolutions limits and therefore lower effective thrust. Tillig and Ringsberg [12] studied the aero- and hydrodynamic interaction effects for wind-assisted cargo ships. In this study they stated that pressure side cavitation is lurking due to low propeller

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loading when wind-assisted propulsion is used. They also state that the CPP is the best propeller to use to handle the varying loads and to avoid pressure side cavitation. In Gypa [13], it is investigated whether a new propeller design can lower the total energy consumption compared to an already existing propeller for a ship retrofitted for wind-assisted propulsion. A new methodology to design a propeller for a wind-assisted propeller is presented for the KVLCC2. It was found that the new propeller design could reduce the total energy consumption by 0.7% compared to the existing propeller. From that it could be concluded that the existing propeller is already close to optimal. In contrast to what Tillig and Ringsberg stated, no issues with respect to pressure side cavitation occurred. One was suggested that issues may occur with the engine reaching its lower torque limit [14]. These light loading conditions could lead to bearing lubrication problems at the shaft [15]. Due to low loading, unburned fuel and soot may leak into the oil pan and dilutes the lubrication oil. This increases the viscosity of the oil and causes the collapse of the critical oil film thickness, which leads to early wear of the engine parts.

Normally, a rudder angle is applied for the ship has to change course. Due to the usage of wind-assisted propulsions, these sails cause a drifting moment on the ship resulting in the ship sailing under a drift angle. In order to restore a straight course, a continuous rudder angle is applied.

In the study of Molland and Turnock [16] it is described that the inflow to the rudder gets straightened by the presence of the propeller and the hull, thus reducing the angle of attack on the rudder. These effects are dependent on the drift angle and thrust loading. When propeller thrust loading increases the straightening effects increase for a drift angle of 15°, but this effect was less or even reversed for 7.5°. Lücke [17] investigated the effect of long-term off-design conditions such as small drift angles on the efficiency and cavitation behavior of a propeller. One outcome was that the propeller thrust increases up to 6% for the same weather conditions when a drift and rudder angles were applied. Badoe [18] studied the lift force on the rudder with changing propeller load. It was found that the lift force on the rudder increases when the propeller load increases. So it is a possibility that the lift generation of the rudder decreases when the propeller load decreases due to wind-assisted propulsion. Due to drift angles of the ship the lift force on the rudder may shift. A study of Tonelli and Vogels [19] also describes the straightening effect of a propeller, which is also dependent on the thrust loading of the propeller. In addition, they describe that the rudder itself blocks and diverts the upstream flow the propeller, which eventually may affect the produced thrust and torque. Moreover, the propeller creates a swirl to the inflow of the propeller, which leads to a shift in the local inflow angle to the rudder. Zhang [20] studied the effect of static drift and rudder angles on the hull resistance, side force, yaw moment and propulsive performance. It was found that with zero drift angle the hull resistance increases by increasing the rudder angle and, by increasing propeller rpm. The study concludes that the influence of the rudder angle on the hull resistance is more profound for non-zero drift angles. Zhang [21] studied the propeller-rudder-hull interaction for a ship with different drift and rudder angles. It was concluded that when a drift angle is applied the hull resistance increases with increasing rudder angle. The presence of a working propeller makes this trend even stronger. The forces on the rudder seem to depend on the propeller. When the propeller performs more work the stall on the rudder delays. Schot and Eggers [22] studied the effect of drift angle on the propeller performance. They found that the effect of drift angle increases when the propeller has a lower rotation rate at the same ship speed. In addition, the propulsive efficiency will change in the order of 2% when the drift angle is varied. In short, the drift angle generates an asymmetric inflow to the propeller and rudder. A working propeller straightens the inflow to the rudder, which delays rudder stall and shifts the lift. This effect is stronger when the work of the propeller is increased. The hull resistance seems to increase with a drift and rudder angle and a working propeller seems to increase this trend. Moreover, the drift angle can have an effect on the propeller efficiency.

To summarize, no study is performed on the effect on the propeller efficiency and hydrodynamic forces when a rudder and drift angle are applied combined with wind-assisted propulsion. Therefore, the focus of this study is to investigate the propeller-rudder-hull interaction for a ship with wind-assisted propulsion. This interaction was investigated in this study by performing CFD computations for the hull with a working propeller for self-propulsion conditions at relevant loading conditions and the most prevalent wind conditions following from routing simulations. Next to this, a propeller optimization study was performed to ensure maximum efficiency. It was also investigated whether the propeller design changes when wind-assisted propulsion is used. The structure of this paper is as follows: First the hull form and test cases are described in Section 2 and 3. Thereafter, the method is described in Section 4. Subsequently, the results and discussions are described in Section 5. Finally, the conclusions and recommendations are given in Section 6.

2. Hull Form

The ship used for this study is a bulk carrier meeting the Newcastlemax constraints. Within the EU project OPTIWISE the hull form was optimized in order to be optimal in terms of power per tons cargo per mile for wind-assisted propulsion. On this optimized ship rotor sails are retrofitted on the ship. The bulk carrier is depicted in Figure 1. The main particulars of the ship are described in Table 1.

Figure 1. Side view

Table 1. Main particulars Newcastlemax

Main particular	Value	unit
Length between perpendiculars	300	[m]
Breadth moulded	50	[m]
Design draught	11	[m]
Scantling draught	18.5	[m]
Displacement volume moulded at scantling draught	233179	[m ³]
Type propulsion	Single screw	[-]

3. Design Conditions

Several test cases were used for this study and are described in Table 2. These test cases were determined from routing simulations. From these routing simulations the 10th, 50th and 90th percentile of the propeller thrust during the journey from Tubarao (Brazil) to Rizhao (China) for scantling and ballast condition, for the return route, were determined with the corresponding weather conditions. To identify the operating conditions matching the percentiles of propeller thrust, the propeller thrust, obtained from the routing simulations, was plotted against the apparent wind angle (blue line), see Figure 2. The ship and wind condition were selected to represent relevant operating conditions for the vessel, i.e., ship speed close to average operating ship speed and wind speed with sufficiently high probability of occurrence. The intersection between the propeller thrust and the target percentile was determined, see intersection of the horizontal line of the percentile thrust (green line) and the propeller thrust (blue line) in Figure 2 obtained for the ballast condition with the 10th percentile propeller thrust. In case of multiple intersections, the point with the smallest apparent wind angle was selected. Once the operating conditions identified, i.e. combination of ship speed wind speed and wind direction, other metrics of the vessel, such as drift and rudder angle and aero force were determined by reading the results from the routing simulations.

Figure 2. 10th percentile propeller thrust and propeller thrust for true wind angle

In Figure 3, it is depicted how the drift and rudder angles are defined. A positive drift angle means that the ship is rotated in clockwise direction, while a negative rudder angle means that the rudder is rotated also in clockwise direction, so the rudder angle in Figure 3 is negative. As can be read in Table 2, for the ballast case, the ship sails with a trim angle to keep the propeller submerged. For ballast case 1 and 3, the ship was pushed down an extra 0.5 m in order to keep the propeller fully submerged to be able to perform the RANS-BEM computation.

Table 2. Test cases for different loading conditions

Loading Condition	Speed [kn]	Tf/Ta [m]	Drift angle [°]	Rudder angle [°]	Aero Force [kN]
Design	11	11/11	0	0	0
Ballast	11	10.170/6.327	0	0	0
Ballast case 1	11	10.670/6.827	2.95	-19.22	732.11
Ballast case 2	11	10.170/6.327	2.58	-9.80	68.97
Ballast case 3	11	10.670/6.827	3.96	-11.85	-68.83
Scantling	11	18.5/18.5	0	0	0
Scantling case 1	11	18.5/18.5	0.95	-11.55	689.25
Scantling case 2	11	18.5/18.5	0.73	-6.28	240.34
Scantling case 3	11	18.5/18.5	1.42	-9.79	120.16

Figure 3. Definition of positive drift and rudder angle.

4. Method

In Figure 4, a schematic overview is given of the steps performed during this study. First, computations are performed on the hull without propeller. From these computations the wakefields are extracted and are used for a first design iteration for the propeller. The resulting propeller is used in a computation with the hull and the rotating propeller. From these computations a wakefield is extracted and used for a second design iteration for the propeller. In this section, all steps performed and programs used are described in further detail.

Figure 4. Schematic overview of the propeller design method

4.1. RANS computations

RANS computations were performed for the design, scantling and ballast conditions without wind-assisted propulsion by using ReFRESCO [23] developed at the Maritime Research Institute Netherlands (MARIN) in collaboration with several universities and partners. It solves (in)compressible viscous flows using the Navier-Stokes equations. These Navier-Stokes equations are complemented with a turbulence model for closure, which for this study is the K-Omega-SST model. The implementation is based on the finite volume method, is collocated and the equations are solved in the cell center [24][25][26]. The continuity, momentum, turbulence and free-surface equations were solved segregated, with a solver based on the SIMPLE pressure-correction algorithm [27]. For the convection term in the momentum equation, a second order total variation diminishing (TVD) harmonic scheme was used with a convergence tolerance of 0.001. For the turbulence equation, an upwind scheme was used with a convergence tolerance of 0.01. For the free-surface equation, the compressive scheme ReFRICS was applied with a convergence tolerance of 0.01. To solve the free-surface simulation, an unsteady approach was used. Therefore, a first order Implicit Euler scheme was used. Thirty outer loops were used per time step. As boundary conditions at the inlet, a ship velocity was applied. At the bottom, top, left, right and outlet a pressure condition was applied. The computations were performed at full scale, including the free surface with dynamic trim and sinkage. The computations were performed for a full ship, since RANS-BEM computations were performed afterwards and later computations were performed with a drift and rudder angle.

Computational domain

Below, details of the computation domain are described for the design condition. The grid is generated with Hexpress [28]. Hexpress generates non-conformal body-fitted full hexahedral unstructured meshes on complex arbitrary geometries. In addition, the advanced smoothing capability provides high quality boundary layers insertion. Figure 5, 6, 7 and 8 show the details of the grid for the design condition for the computation without propeller.

Table 3. Information computational domain

Parameters (design condition)	grid	Value
Dimensions		6.0 x 4.0 x 4.0 Lpp
Grid type		Unstructured
Number of cells		22 676 143

Figure 5. 3D domain bird view

Figure 6. Surface grid, oblique fish-eye view on the bow

Figure 7. Surface grid, oblique fish-eye view on the stern

Figure 8. Volume grid at the water plane, top view

4.2. Propeller optimization study with PROPART

Nominal wakefields and the hydrodynamic force on the hull result from the RANS computations. The nominal wakefields and hydrodynamic force are used for the propeller optimization study using PROPART, a MATLAB toolbox developed by MARIN and used to design the F-series propellers. PROPART typically balances the propeller efficiency by noise and vibration, and, cavitation erosion risk. It uses a parametric description of the propeller and tries to find the most optimal propeller within the given input and settings. Within each optimization round, a PROCAL [29] computation is performed, which is a boundary element method (BEM) that computes the inviscid flow around the propeller. The results from PROCAL are converted into new objectives and constraints for PROPART. The result of the optimization study is a Pareto front.

The propeller is designed for the design condition with the rps specified by the optimizer, the pitch of the propeller is scaled to obtain the required thrust. For the ballast and scantling condition the rate of revolutions are varied in order to obtain the required thrust for that condition. A constraint is given regarding the matching of the propeller with the engine. An engine and propeller curve of the used engine is shown in Figure 9. The working point of the propeller for the design condition should be within a bandwidth of 10% from the propeller curve. The optimization algorithm used by PROPART is CMOPSO [30] extended to use Deb's parameterless method for constraint handling [31]. In addition, the propeller should adhere to defined class rules, which is for this study from the class society DNV. Another constraint is that risk on erosion should be minimal.

Figure 9. Engine and propeller curve with lower and upper limit for the propeller

4.3. RANS-BEM computations (ReFRESKO – PROCAL/PROPART)

After a propeller is chosen from the propeller optimization study by Propart, RANS-BEM computations were performed. With the RANS-BEM coupling procedure a steady RANS (ReFRESKO) computation for the viscous flow around the ship is coupled with an unsteady BEM (Procal) computation to model the action of the propeller [32]. An overview of the workflow of the RANS-BEM coupling is depicted in Figure 10, which shows an iterative process. It couples the velocity fields from the RANS and BEM computations with the force distribution on the propeller blades from the BEM computations. The procedure is as follows:

1. The nominal wake field is determined by performing RANS computations without a propeller. The nominal wake field is determined at the location of the propeller plane.
2. An unsteady BEM computation is performed to determine the loading distribution on the propeller blades and the average force on the camber plane by using the nominal wake field from step 1 as a first estimate for the effective wake field. From this, a three-dimensional time-averaged force distribution is constructed.
3. The result from step 2 is applied as body force field in a RANS computation. To do that, the force distribution from the BEM computation is interpolated to the RANS grid.
4. To obtain the effective wake field a total wake field is computed with RANS from where the propeller induced velocities are subtracted, which are computed by the BEM computation.
5. Step 2-4 are repeated until convergence is reached with respect to thrust and effective wake velocities between the RANS and BEM computations.

Figure 10. Schematic overview of RANS-BEM coupling procedure

4.4. Second propeller optimization with effective wakefields

From the RANS-BEM computations, effective wake fields result. Another round of propeller optimization was performed with these effective wake fields from the condition without and with wind-assisted propulsion. This second optimization round was performed to investigate whether the propeller performance and design changes when wind-assisted propulsion is used. To perform this study, the PROPART script used for the first optimization round was used and appended by the extra conditions from wind-assisted propulsion. All constraints regarding cavitation were specified to all these conditions.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 First optimization phase with PROPART

This section describes the results of the first propeller optimization round with PROPART. The resulting Pareto front is shown in Figure 11. On the x-axis the power needed by the engine is plotted with on the y-axis the virtual force on the hull. The virtual force is a force that is derived from the pressure fluctuations which result from the

BEM calculations. The hull is not present in these BEM calculations, so there is no scattering and interference, so this force on the hull is a virtual force and only in the vertical direction. The virtual force is taken as optimization goal to minimize. For the cavitation and erosion, empirical models are used to estimate the amount of cavitation and erosion. Constraint values are set for the cavitation and erosion and when the propeller is not meeting these constraints, the propeller is rejected. The propeller used for the RANS-BEM computations is highlighted. From this graph an estimate of the cost of minimizing the cavitation (volume variations) on efficiency is apparent for the entire design space of the propeller.

For the successive RANS-BEM computations, a propeller was chosen in the middle of the Pareto front, which is highlighted in Figure 11. As described in Section 4.2, the propeller is matched with the engine installed. In Figure 12, the working point of the propeller for the three wind conditions is shown in the engine diagram, while this constraint was only applied to the design condition the propeller works within the determined bandwidth for all the three conditions. It was observed that the optimizer always selected designs at the upper bandwidth in an attempt to minimize the rate of revolutions.

Figure 11. Pareto front first phase of propeller optimization without wind-assisted propulsion. The chosen propeller is highlighted.

Figure 12. Engine diagram with working points propeller for each condition

5.2 Propeller thrust and hydrodynamic forces

Figures 13 and 14 show the net hydrodynamic forces on the hull for the ballast and scantling conditions with the corresponding wind-assisted propulsion (green bar) and the required propeller thrust (red bar). The net hydrodynamic force on the hull (blue bar) is larger for the cases with wind-assisted propulsion. This is expected, since the ship sails for these conditions with a drift and rudder angle. The orange bar, shows the net hydrodynamic force on the hull with propeller action. The difference between the blue and orange bar is the thrust deduction. For ballast case 1, this difference is almost zero. This is due to the small propeller thrust that is required, since the wind-assisted propulsion delivers almost all the required thrust. On the other hand, the thrust deduction for ballast case 2 and 3 is large. This is because the net effect of wind-assisted propulsion is small or even negative for these cases. It is observed that the net force of the wind propulsion is positive, but the added resistance by sailing at a drift angle negates much of the advantage, compounded by the effect of deteriorating thrust deduction by the increased propeller loading.

From the plot for the ballast conditions, it can even be concluded that for ballast case 2 and 3 the propeller should perform more work in comparison to the condition without wind-assisted propulsion. Therefore, it can be concluded that for these cases it is inefficient to use wind-assisted propulsion.

For the scantling conditions, see Figure 14, it is advantageous for all cases to use wind-assisted propulsion. A remarkable result is that the net hydrodynamic hull force with propeller is small for the scantling condition 1 and 2 than for the case without wind-assisted propulsion. Even though the ship sails with a drift and rudder angle, the resistance on the hull is smaller. This is due to the small thrust deduction, since most thrust is performed by the wind-assisted propulsion.

Figure 13. Hydrodynamic hull forces with and without propeller, aero force and required propeller thrust for ballast conditions

Figure 14. Hydrodynamic hull forces with and without propeller, aero force and required propeller thrust for scantling conditions

In the Figures 15, 16 and 17, the components of the net hydrodynamic force on the hull are split out. The blue bar represents the cases without propeller action and the orange bar represents the cases with propeller action. The first observation is that for the ballast conditions, the resistance of the rudder is a large component of the total resistance, especially for case 1. This is due to the large rudder angle in combination with the drift angle, resulted in flow separation at the rudder. In Figure 18, the regions of flow separation are depicted. It clearly shows the large region of flow separation for case 1 in comparison to case 2 and 3.

Another striking result is that the rudder is generating a small thrust for the scantling conditions without propeller. This is due to the combination of the drift and rudder angles. When the propeller action is applied, for cases 1 and 3, this thrust disappears due to flow straightening effect of the propeller. For case 2, this small thrust is still present even when propeller action is applied.

Figure 15. Resistance composition in percentage design condition

Figure 16. Resistance composition in percentage ballast condition

Figure 17. Resistance composition in percentage scantling condition

Figure 18. Flow separation on the rudder (magenta regions) for ballast case 1, 2 and 3

5.3 Propeller Performance and Design

After the RANS-BEM computations were performed, another propeller optimization round was performed with PROPART by using the effective wakefields. In Figure 19, the resulting Pareto front together with the Pareto front from the first optimization round is shown. On the x-axis the required engine power with on the y-axis the virtual

force on the hull surface. The front with the blue circles represents the optimization study for the conditions without-wind assisted propulsion. The orange circles represent the optimization study with wind-assisted propulsion. Both Pareto fronts are more or less on the same position. This means that, although wind-assisted propulsion is used and the ship is sailing with a drift and rudder angle, that the constraints on cavitation behavior for these conditions does not impact the overall trade-off. The propeller will not perform less in view of virtual force and needed power.

Figure 19. Pareto fronts for conditions without wind-assisted propulsion (blue) and for conditions with wind-assisted propulsion (orange).

Below, in Figure 20, the propeller working points are plotted in the engine diagram for all conditions. Most working points are within the set bandwidth, even though the restriction is only set for the design condition. Only for ballast case 1 and 3 and scantling case 1, the propeller works outside this bandwidth. This is because for ballast and scantling case 1, the propeller only needs to deliver a small amount of thrust. For ballast case 3, the propeller should deliver a large amount of thrust. Unfortunately, lubrication problems can occur at the shaft when the propeller produces is running with a low rpm and works outside the bandwidth.

Figure 20. Working points propeller in engine diagram for all conditions

Next to the performance, also the difference in propeller design is investigated between the propellers designed without wind-assisted propulsion taken into account and the propeller with wind assisted propulsion taken into account. In Figure 21 the pitch distribution is displayed. The blue curves represent the without wind-assisted propulsion propellers and the orange curves with wind-assisted propulsion. For the pitch distribution, no significant difference can be found between the two sets of propellers.

Figure 21. Pitch distribution of propellers without wind-assisted propulsion (blue) and with wind-assisted propulsion (orange)

Since no significant differences in performances and design were found for the two sets of propellers, another test case was performed. The propellers designed by PROPART for the case without wind-assisted propulsion, the first optimization round, were put into the wind-assisted propulsion conditions. It was investigated whether the performance of these propellers lie behind the Pareto front or would violate a constraint. The results are shown in Figure 22. In yellow, the propellers are shown with a line to the case with wind. The performance goes down, but the difference is very small.

Figure 22. Performance of propellers in each other's condition

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, a propeller optimization study was performed for a bulk carrier with wind-assisted propulsion. A closer look was taken at the propeller-rudder-hull interaction by performing RANS-BEM calculations for self-propulsion conditions at the relevant loading conditions and most prevalent wind conditions following from routing simulations. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- The net hydrodynamic hull force without propeller action increases for all conditions with wind-assisted propulsion due to the drift and rudder angle applied.
 - A significant larger net hydrodynamic hull force is found for ballast case 1 due to flow separation at the rudder due to the large rudder angle.
- The required propeller thrust decreases when wind-assisted propulsion used for most cases.
 - This is not the case for ballast case 2 and 3, with low and negative aero force, since the wind-assisted propulsion is too small to compensate for the increase in hydrodynamic hull force due to the drift and rudder angle.
- The thrust deduction decreases for wind-assisted propulsion in most cases, since less propeller thrust is required.
- The rudder for scantling condition case 2 generates thrust due to convenient combination of drift and rudder angle.
- No significant difference in propeller performance is found for propellers optimized without and with taking the conditions for wind-assisted propulsion into account.
- No significant difference is found in the propeller design between propeller design without wind-assisted propulsion and with wind-assisted propulsion.
- No significant difference in performance is found when propellers not designed for wind-assisted propulsion are used in wind-assisted propulsion conditions.

The overall conclusion is that for a bulk carrier with wind assisted-propulsion by rotor sails, no special needs are present regarding the propeller design. The propeller designed for conditions without wind-propulsion and without rudder and drift angles performance more or less the same in conditions with wind-assisted propulsion.

On the other hand, it is advised to perform the same study for other ship types. The bulk carrier is a ship with a high block coefficient, therefore it is recommended to perform this study also for ships which are more slender and have a smaller block coefficient. It is also recommended to perform a more detailed study on the manoeuvrability. Flow separation may occur at the rudder due to the combination of drift and rudder angles. This could affect the manoeuvrability of the ship. In conclusion it is recommended to investigate the effect on the engine when the propeller is running light. It should be investigated whether bearing problems occur at the shaft.

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